

Pythagorean-Like Formulas for any Triangle

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 15 December 2022	We propose two generalizations of Pythagoras' theorem from which the cosine law immediately follows.
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I. INTRODUCTION

In [1], L. Hoehn, by using the tangent-secant theorem, (sometimes called Steiner's Theorem), obtains an elegant proof of Pythagoras' theorem and also tries a Pythagorean-like formula for isosceles triangles. In [2], the author generalizes the previous result to any triangle.

In the following we extend this results through the concept of cevian, providing some Pythagorean-like formulas valid for each triangle (Theorems 1 and 2), from which immediately follows the law of cosines.

Moreover, based on the same idea, we try a simple proof of the converse of Pythagoras' theorem (Theorem 3).

II. PYTAGOREAN-LIKE FORMULAS

Theorem 1. Let a, b, c , with $a \geq b$, be the lengths of the sides of a triangle. Let d be the length of the projection of a onto c , obtained by the cevian congruent to b . Then, $a^2 = b^2 + cd$.

In particular, if the angle opposite to the side a is right, then $a^2 = b^2 + c^2$.

Proof. Given a triangle ABC with $BC = a \geq AC = b$ and $AB = c$, construct the circle with centre C and radius b as shown in Figures 1 and 2. By using the two secant theorem, we have $(a+b)(a-b) = cd$, then, $a^2 = b^2 + cd$.

Fig. 1: Case $a \leq c$, $(a+b)(a-b) = cd$, i.e. $a^2 = b^2 + cd$

Fig. 2: Case $a > c$, $(a+b)(a-b) = cd$, i.e. $a^2 = b^2 + cd$

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In particular, if \hat{BAC} is a right angle, then $c = d$, so we have Pythagoras' theorem. \square

Similarly, in the case $BC = a \leq AC = b$, by using the intersecting chords theorem as shown in Figures 3 and 4, we can see that $DB : AB = BF : BE$, i.e. $(b-a) : c = d : (b+a)$. Therefore we can prove the following statement.

Theorem 2. Let a, b, c , with $a \leq b$, be the lengths of the sides of a triangle. Let d be the length of the projection of a onto c , obtained by the cevian congruent to b . Then, $a^2 = b^2 - cd$.

In particular, if the angle opposite to the side b is right, then $a^2 = b^2 - c^2$.

Proof.

Fig. 3: Case $b \geq c$, $(b-a)(b+a) = cd$, i.e. $a^2 = b^2 - cd$

Fig. 4: Case $b < c$, $(b-a)(b+a) = cd$, i.e. $a^2 = b^2 - cd$.

Analyzing the diagrams in Figure 1, we can also derive that $c-d=2b \cos \hat{BAC}$. Similarly, analyzing the diagrams in Figure 2, we can see that $c+d=2b \cos \hat{BAC}$. In each of the previous cases we have $a^2=b^2+c(c-2b \cos \hat{BAC})$, from which follows the cosine law, that for completeness we enunciate below.

Corollary. Let a, b, c be the lengths of the sides of a triangle and let α the width of the angle opposite to the a side, then $a^2=b^2+c^2-2bc \cos \alpha$.

Finally, thinking by exclusion about the diagrams in Figure 1, we can also try a simple proof of the converse of Pythagoras' Theorem.

Theorem 3. Let a, b, c be the lengths of the sides of a triangle and let $a^2=b^2+c^2$. Then the angle opposite to the side a is right.

Proof. Given a triangle ABC , with $BC=a, AC=b, AB=c$ and $a^2=b^2+c^2$, we have $a > b$. Then the circle with center C and radius b intersects the BC side in a point D , as in the previous Figures 1 and 2.

Let F be the other point where this circle intersects the AB side (or its extended side), and let $FB=d$. By $FC=b$, follows that FB is the projection of a onto c obtained by the cevian congruent to b . Then, for Theorem 1, we have $a^2=b^2+cd$ and a quick comparison with the hypothesis $a^2=b^2+c^2$ yields the conclusion that $c=d$.

Then A and F are coincident, so the segment AB is tangent to the circle, which implies that the angle \hat{BAC} is right.

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